

Ionic Adsorption at Hg/NH₄Cl (aqueous) Interface[‡]

M. V. RAMANAMURTI and NAVIN CHANDRA*

Chemistry Department, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi 221 005 (India)

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The differential capacity of the Hg/NH₄Cl solution interface has been measured by symmetrical Wien type a.c. bridge for eight concentrations of aqueous NH₄Cl in the potential range -0.10 to -1.40 volts (versus normal calomel electrode). The charge due to surface excess of cations and anions, charge due to any excess or deficiency of anions in the diffuse layer and the charge due to specific adsorption of anions have been calculated and their dependence on electrode potential and electrolyte concentration have been discussed.

THE electrical double layer formed at electrode/electrolyte interface plays an important role and affects the reactions taking place at an electrode. For proper understanding of electrode kinetics and interpretation of the results obtained by many modern analytical techniques, the knowledge of structure and behaviour of electrical double layer is essential.

Exhaustive scanning of the literature indicates that the chemical and electrical potential dependence of ionic adsorption at Hg/NH₄Cl interface has not been properly studied. The present paper reports the results of intensive studies of this interface.

Experimental

Test solutions were prepared with AnalaR (B.D.H.) NH₄Cl which was recrystallized twice in conductivity water. Conductivity water (specific conductivity 0.1 - 0.2 × 10⁻⁸ mho/cm) was prepared by distilling double distilled water with alkaline KMnO₄ in an all-Pyrex-glass set. The middle cut was collected and stored in Pyrex-glass ground stoppered reagent bottles.

Mercury purified by standard procedure¹ was distilled twice in an all Pyrex-glass set under vacuum and used in dropping mercury electrode (DME).

A cylindrical glass vessel with a ground glass cap fitted with five standard joints which facilitated to insert DME, lead to mercury pool, salt bridge to the reference electrode, nitrogen gas delivery tube and a glass spoon used to determine mercury flow rate, was used as electrolytic cell. The cell cap was provided with a pin hole to act as outlet for nitrogen,

A symmetrical Wien's bridge designed for the measurement of resistance and capacitance in series, similar to that of Grahame^{2,3}, was used. Two noninductive noncapacitative standard resistances of 1000 ohms each were used in ratio arms. The measuring

standards were Muirhead decade condenser of 1.110 μfarad variable in steps of 0.001 μfarad and a noninductive noncapacitative a.c./d.c. Leeds & Northrup decade resistor of 11110 ohms variable in steps of 0.1 ohm. The output signal of the bridge was amplified by a multistage transistor preamplifier (Marcony type TM 6591A) and fed to a Dumont oscilloscope (type 274). Marcony R. C. oscillator (type TF 1370) was used as the input generator of the bridge. The differential capacity of the Hg/NH₄Cl interface was independent of the frequency. The differential capacity measurements were done at 1000 Hz.

The cell, DME and reference electrode were accommodated in an air thermostated glass chamber. The test solutions were preelectrolysed and deaerated with purified 'high purity' tank nitrogen. The differential capacity measurements were done at 20 millivolt interval of potential in the potential range -0.10 to -1.40 volt at 25 ± 0.1°. The reference electrode was a 1N KCl calomel electrode. The surface area of the drop was calculated from the rate of mercury flow and the age of the drop. A locally fabricated drop detacher was used to knock off the drop at a prefixed age of the drop. The potential of zero charge (PZC) was determined by differentiation of electrocapillary curves obtained by drop time technique.

Surface charge density of mercury (q^M) was obtained by integrating differential capacity (C) versus potential curves. The integration constant was evaluated from the knowledge of the PZC. The activity coefficients for aqueous NH₄Cl solutions were taken from literature⁴. Using the relations developed by Grahame⁵ and Grahame and Soderberg⁶, the charge due to surface excess of cations (Γ₊Z₊F) and anions (Γ₋Z₋F) and the charge due to any excess or deficiency of anions in the diffuse layer (q^d) and charge due to specifically adsorbed anions (q¹) were calculated for 0.10, 0.25, 0.50 and 1.00m NH₄Cl solutions.

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* Present Address : Fundamental Division, Central Electrochemical Research Institute, Karai Kudi-623 006

Results and Discussion

The chemical and electrical potential dependence of differential capacity of Hg/NH₄Cl aqueous solution interface is shown in figure 1. The main features of capacity curves are observation of (i) a minimum in capacity (C_{min}) at ≈ 1.10 volt, (ii) a sharp rise in capacity at extreme anodic potentials with reference to PZC and (iii) a hump at intermediate potentials. The hump is more pronounced in concentrated solutions than in dilute solutions.

The rise in capacity with increasing cathodic potentials beyond C_{min} is attributed to the overpowering of the effect of electrostriction of water over the dielectric saturation effect on capacity at such high cathodic potentials of the DME^{7,8}. Grahame attributes the sharp rise in capacity at extreme anodic potentials (with reference to PZC) also to the electrostriction of solvents. The view gains further support from the observation⁹ of more sharp rise in more compressible solvents (e.g. methanol) than in less compressible solvents (e.g. water) and the increase of sharpness with increasing methanol content in electrolyte solutions made in methanol-water mixtures¹⁰. However, a more sharp rise at extreme anodic potentials than at cathodic potentials beyond C_{min} for any system suggests that electrostriction is not solely responsible for rise in capacity at extreme anodic potentials. Hills¹¹ suggested that faradaic processes whereby anions are ultimately discharged at the metal surface are responsible for rise in capacity at extreme anodic potentials. Harrison *et al.*¹² suggested that the positive charge at mercury drop is present as discrete ions and anions interact

Figure 1. Potential dependence of differential capacity at Hg/NH₄Cl (aqueous) solution interface at 25°C. The concentration of NH₄Cl is indicated on the curves.

more strongly with them than the cations would do with negative charge present as smeared out electron cloud. The strong positive polarisation of mercury thus produces roughening of the metal surface. It seems more probable that roughening of the mercury surface is also responsible for sharp rise in capacity at extreme anodic potentials (with reference to PZC) in addition to electrostriction of solvent in the inner layer.

The occurrence of hump in aqueous electrolyte solutions has been attributed by Shvarts *et al.*¹³ to the 'arrest' of specific adsorption of anions due to decrease in the number of water molecules adsorbed with their negative end toward mercury at PZC caused by high polarising power (capable of forming hydration shell) of anions. The observation of a predominant hump in present system (cf. figure 1) is easily understandable in the high polarising power of chloride ion.

Figure 2. Potential dependence of charge density of the metal surface (q^M) at Hg/NH₄Cl (aqueous) solution interface. The concentration of NH₄Cl is indicated on the curves.

The surface charge density of mercury (q^M) versus potential curves for 0.10, 0.25, 0.50 and 1.00 m solutions are shown in figure 2. As the polarisation potential of the DME is increased in magnitude, the positive values of q^M decrease through zero (at PZC) and become negative whereafter their magnitude increases (cf. figure 2).

Figure 3 illustrates the dependence of Γ_+Z_+F and Γ_-Z_-F on electrode potential and electrolyte concentration. In absence of cation specific adsorption as in the present case, Γ_+Z_+F represents the excess or deficiency of cations in the diffuse layer and is controlled by the charge (with sign) on the electrode side of the outer Helmholtz plane (OHP). The Γ_+Z_+F is positive throughout the potential range and for all the concentrations of NH_4Cl studied. Also, the Γ_+Z_+F passes through a minimum (Γ_+^{min}) at an intermediate potential and the potential of Γ_+^{min} shifts to more cathodic potentials with increase in NH_4Cl concentration. The positive values of Γ_+Z_+F at PZC and at anodic potentials with reference to PZC are attributed to the specific adsorption of anions whereby the net charge on the electrode side of the OHP becomes negative⁵. The rise in Γ_+Z_+F with increasing anodic potential with reference to Γ_+^{min} is due to a higher rate of increase of negative charge in the inner layer due to specific adsorption of anions than the rate of increase of positive charge on the mercury surface i.e., $|dq^1/dE| > |dq^M/dE|$ (cf. figures 2 and 4). Similarly, with increasing cathodic potentials beyond Γ_+^{min} the rise in Γ_+Z_+F is caused by higher rate of increase of negative charge on the metal surface with potential than

NH_4Cl concentration at anodic and small cathodic potentials with reference to PZC indicates increasing specific adsorption of anions with increase in bulk electrolyte concentration.

The Γ_-Z_-F (cf. figure 3) starting with a positive value decreases through zero to become negative whereafter its magnitude increases as the magnitude of the cathodic potential of the DME is decreased. The positive (negative) values of Γ_-Z_-F are indicative of deficiency (excess) of anions in the double layer. Γ_-Z_-F comprises of two parts. q^d and q^1 .

q^d is positive (indicating deficiency of Cl^- ions in the diffuse layer) for all the four concentrations of NH_4Cl throughout the potential range (cf. figure 4). Like Γ_+Z_+F for cations, q^d represents the charge due to any excess or deficiency of anions in the diffuse layer and hence is dependent on the sign and magnitude of the charge on the electrode side of the OHP. Similar to Γ_+Z_+F curves, q^d curves also show a minimum. The potential of minimum in Γ_+Z_+F and q^d curves are identical for any fixed concentration of electrolyte. The minimum in q^d and the rise on either side of this minimum also are explainable in terms of the magnitudes of dq^M/dE and dq^1/dE . With increasing electrolyte concentration the increase in q^d indicates that the deficiency of anions in the diffuse layer increases.

Figure 3. Potential dependence of charge due to surface excess of cations (Γ_+Z_+F) and anions (Γ_-Z_-F) at $\text{Hg}/\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ (aqueous) solution interface. The concentration of electrolyte is indicated on the curves.

the rate of desorption of anions from the inner layer i.e., $|dq^1/dE| < |dq^M/dE|$ (cf. figures 2 and 4). At Γ_+^{min} , $|dq^1/dE| = |dq^M/dE|$. The shift of Γ_+^{min} to more cathodic potentials with increase in electrolyte concentration is understandable in increase of rate of specific adsorption of anions. The increase of Γ_+Z_+F with

Figure 4. Potential dependence of charge due to any excess or deficiency of anions in the diffuse layer (q^d) and specifically adsorbed anions (q^1). The concentration of electrolyte is indicated on the curves.

q^1 , the charge due to specific adsorption of anions is zero (indicating complete desorption of anions from

the inner layer) at extreme cathodic potentials of the DME and as the magnitude of the cathodic potential is decreased, the magnitude of the negative values of q^1 increases (cf. figure 4). The potential of complete desorption of anions from the inner layer shifts to more cathodic potentials with increase in Cl⁻ concentration in the bulk of the solution. At any potential, with increase in electrolyte concentration, the specific adsorption of chloride ions increases.

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